

ATTENTION TO YOUTH - ATTENTION TO THE FUTURE

¹Akhmedova M., ²Alimova M.M., ³Abdusattorov S.Sh.

^{1,2}Tashkent Pediatric Medical Institute

³Teacher at the Institute of ISFT

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14011635>

Abstract. *The article analyzes the opportunities and benefits created for the youth of New Uzbekistan. Recommendations were also given regarding the means and opportunities for independent work of young people in all areas.*

Keywords: *youth, rights, responsibilities, state youth policy, parliamentary control, five initiatives, youth parliament, competitions, creativity, entrepreneurship, innovative projects.*

Relevance: It is known that the education of the younger generation has always been important and relevant. But in the 21st century, in which we live, this issue really becomes a matter of life and death. Today, the priority is the education of young people who think in a new way, have their own independent worldview, approach the events happening around them with a sense of involvement, and have a strong civic position. In this regard, our state takes responsibility for the future of its youth and pays special attention to the issue of the continuity of our youth for the future in building a legal democratic state and civil society. The goal of the reforms implemented in our country to create broad conditions for young people and continuing to this day is the formation of a young generation worthy of this trust and attention. That is why today we all need to pay attention to issues of ensuring youth employment, the widespread use of their opportunities, and regular work with unorganized youth in the regions. It should be understood that this year has been called the "Year of Youth and Business Support" as a consistent continuation of the implementation of state policy towards youth. After all, youth is the decisive force of the state and society. Today, it is impossible to imagine a modern economy without large-scale underdeveloped business. The year 2023, which has come to an end, was marked in history by rich details of political events in the life of our country. All corners of our country have turned into huge construction and creative fields.

The purpose of this study: Today, along with government agencies, such organizations as the Youth Union of Uzbekistan, the El-Yurt Umidi Foundation and many other non-governmental public organizations work in the field of youth policy. The head of the country put forward an initiative to transform the previously known youth movement "Kamolot" into the Youth Union of Uzbekistan. The decision on the transformation was also reflected in the Presidential Decree of July 5 of that 2017. In accordance with this document, June 30 was declared Youth Day. Since the creation of the Youth Union of Uzbekistan, the organization has been working to form a harmoniously developed new generation, historical consciousness and historical memory, promote a healthy lifestyle and environmental culture, increase a sense of patriotism, protect rights and legitimate interests, support young people seeking to master modern professions, develop youth entrepreneurship, protect young men and women from the influence of destructive and religious ideas and other areas.

In particular, the legislation adopted by our government guarantees the rights and interests of the youth of Uzbekistan, creates the basis for young people to achieve new heights and make a worthy contribution to the development of our country. It is known that if we look at history, then

before independence and in the first years of independence, the attitude towards the life of young people, their ideas were not given much attention. Today, in his speeches and appearances, President Sh. Mirziyoyev emphasizes the need to pay special attention to young people, that they are the main link in the chain of state governance. The first law signed by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh. Mirziyoyev on September 14, 2016, is the Law "On State Youth Policy" in order to protect the rights and interests of the youth of our country, create the necessary conditions and opportunities for them became the basis for work. It is no coincidence that 2021 was declared by our President in our country as the Year of Youth Support and Public Health. We can say with confidence that this event was the first step in supporting young people.

Materials and methods of research: Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated March 2, 2020 "On the State Program for the Implementation of the Action Strategy for Five Priority Areas of Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2017-2021" in the Year of Science, Education and Digital Economy was adopted. In order to ensure the implementation of paragraph 21 of this state program, the "Youth Parliament" was created. The number of deputies of the Youth Parliament under the Senate of Oliy Majlis has reached 100, and the number of deputies of the Youth Parliament under the Legislative Chamber of Oliy Majlis has reached 150. Currently, the youth parliament is directly involved in solving all kinds of problems of our people.

First of all, the noble work of the deputies of the Youth Parliament indicates that the living conditions of the population living in remote areas of the country are being studied, problems and shortcomings are being eliminated. Wherever we go in the world, young people are not given such opportunities.

In Uzbekistan, the youth issue has risen to the level of state policy. The initiative "Supporting the youth in parliament" was also put forward, and on the recommendation of the Council of People's Deputies, it was recommended to assign young, purposeful, and courageous young people to the deputies of the Legislative Chamber and the Senate. Such work serves as the basis for the direct participation of young people in parliamentary activities. In particular, members of the Youth Parliament take direct part in the sessions of Oliy Majlis. They also have the opportunity to make proposals to Oliy Majlis on the initiative of the draft law [3]. It should be noted that repair work in educational institutions is currently under the control of the Youth Parliament. Member of the Science Commission of the Youth Parliament under the Senate of Oliy Majlis, head of the secretariat of the Yakkabag District Council, deputy Sh. Yusupov visited the 14th specialized state comprehensive school in his district and got acquainted with the progress and quality of repair work. Also, on the state of preparation for the 2021-2022 academic year, the state of construction work in schools and buildings allocated for the elections of comprehensive schools 44-45-46, located in the makhallas of "Tolbulak", "Faizabad", "Said-ota" in Tashkent region. Also he took an active part in parliamentary control activities for the purpose of training. These matters were taken under control by deputies of the youth parliament. Together they solve important problems. Wherever we go in the country, favorable conditions for youth activities have been created in all regions. In particular, it should be noted that youth policy has reached every region, every city and every village of the country. Taking advantage of such conditions, young people strive to show their talents in all areas, increase their knowledge, skills and experience in all areas, and boldly achieve high results. All political processes in our country are carried out at a high level and with great responsibility. In particular, the political process in our country, the presidential elections were held in an elevated mood and at a high level, which emphasized the

activity of young people. Before that, electoral districts were created in each region of the country, and our youth took an active part in the election campaign.

Researches and discussion: One of the important events of 2019 for young people are the five important initiatives put forward by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev for the systematic implementation of measures in the social and spiritual-educational fields, which marked the beginning of a new stage in the upbringing and education of young people in the history of Uzbekistan. It is also worth noting that the country has created all the necessary conditions for training and professional activity, and the five most important initiatives serve as the main mechanism for the manifestation of the abilities of young people.

And so, as a result of the systematic work carried out to form a "youth notebook", as well as for the purpose of high-quality implementation of the tasks assigned by the head of state, the following results have been achieved:

A single electronic platform daftar.mehnat.uz was created on the basis of the interdepartmental software and hardware complex "Unified National Labor System".

The Agency for Youth Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan is creating "Youth Media Centers and Schools for Young Journalists" in the regions.

In general, in the last four years, the youth policy of the Republic of Uzbekistan has been gaining new horizons and has the support of the younger generation. All of the above reforms serve as a greater lever and motivation for them to achieve certain goals in life.

REFERENCES

1. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated February 7, 2017 No. UP-4947. - Tashkent. 2001. - 9.T. "Uzbekistan". P.
2. Website of the center "Tarakkiyot strategiasi" www.strategy.uz
3. Mukhiddinova F. Scientific publication "Future youth of the new Uzbekistan: opportunities and legal guarantees". <https://yuz.uz/uz> Information service of the Senate of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan. <https://senat.uz> Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-5953 dated March 2, 2020 "On the State Program for the implementation of the Action Strategy for five priority areas of development of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2017-2021 in the Year of Science, Education and Digital Economy."
4. <https://www.uzdaily.ru/post/38154/B> Узбекистане принята государственная программа Yoshlar - kelajagimiz.
5. <https://www.univ-silkroad.ru/news/novosti-universiteta/item/408-the-five-initiatives/> Пять важных инициатив в действии.